

Workshop on Change Languages in Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs

2023-05-09

8am-11am PT

Purpose of this workshop

Goals

- Develop a shared concept of ontology change
- Gather community requirements
- Circulate proposed KGCL standard
- Gather feedback on
 - Change types
 - Change syntax
- Feedback on BioPortal change request UI

Audience

- Ontology users - biocurators, data scientists
- Ontology developers
- Tool builders

Agenda ([link](#))

Part I: Intro to KGCL; demos

Part 2: Use cases and discussion

Change is important for ontologies

Ontologies and knowledge bases are not static!

Changes happen in response to

- New knowledge
- New terminology
- Improved modeling of knowledge
- **Requests from community**

Change is central to what we do!
And yet...

Changes in GO terms between releases

...yet we lack a standard terminology for change

What changed
between v1 and
v2?

1252 new axioms
987 deleted axioms

Hmm, that's a bit
abstract for me

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<diffReport>
<diffSummary>
<numberChangedClasses>
209
</numberChangedClasses>
<numberNewClasses>
88
</numberNewClasses>
<numberDeletedClasses>
0
</numberDeletedClasses>
</diffSummary>
<changedClasses>
<changedClass>
<classIRI>http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_2100395</classIRI>
<classLabel>cerebrospinal fluid monocyte count assay</classLabel>
<newAxiom>&apos;cerebrospinal fluid monocyte count assay&apos; SubClassOf
&apos;cerebrospinal fluid assay&apos;</newAxiom>
</changedClass>
<changedClass>
<classIRI>http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_2100396</classIRI>
<classLabel>cerebrospinal fluid eosinophil count assay</classLabel>
<newAxiom>&apos;cerebrospinal fluid eosinophil count assay&apos; SubClassOf
&apos;cerebrospinal fluid assay&apos;</newAxiom>
</changedClass>
</changedClasses>
```

...yet we lack a standard terminology for change

What changed
between v1 and
v2?

Still a bit abstract

central and lateral incisor tooth #2757

Open megbalk wants to merge 5 commits into `master` from `issue-2719`

Conversation 5 Commits 5 Checks 3 Files changed 1

Changes from all commits File filter Conversations Jump to

36 `src/ontology/uberon-edit.obo`

			<code>@@ -168149,6 +168149,7 @@ subset: pheno_slim</code>
168149	168149		synonym: "maxillary central permanent incisor tooth" EXACT []
168150	168150		synonym: "maxillary central secondary incisor tooth" EXACT [FMA:55722]
168151	168151		synonym: "permanent upper central incisor tooth" RELATED [FMA:55722]
	168152	+	synonym: "secondary upper first incisor tooth" EXACT []
168152	168153		synonym: "upper central permanent incisor tooth" EXACT [FMA:55722]
168153	168154		xref: FMA:55722
168154	168155		intersection_of: UBERON:0001098 ! incisor tooth
			<code>@@ -168161,6 +168162,7 @@ id: UBERON:0016455</code>
168161	168162		name: upper lateral secondary incisor tooth
168162	168163		subset: pheno_slim
168163	168164		synonym: "maxillary lateral secondary incisor tooth" EXACT [FMA:55724]
	168165	+	synonym: "secondary upper second incisor tooth" EXACT []

...yet we lack a standard terminology for change

What changed
between v1 and
v2?

That tells me a bit
more... I think I know
what “**Valid**” is... but
what’s “**Merged**”?
Sounds like GO jargon

GENEONTOLOGY
Unifying Biology

About

Ontology

Annotations

Downloads

|

Release statistics

In this section, the statistics of GO can be browsed for any of the releases archive

Statistics for release

Ontology

Property	Value	Ar
Valid terms	43096 ($\Delta = -152$)	Pr
Obsoleted terms	4388 ($\Delta = 219$)	Nu
Merged terms	2441 ($\Delta = 0$)	Ar
Biological process terms	27790	Ar
Molecular function terms	11263	Ar
Cellular component terms	4043	Ar

<http://geneontology.org/stats.html>

Releases Tags

Mar 23

jamesaoverton

v2023-03-10

b20ee2f

Compare

This is great.. But I wish it showed more than just new terms

2023-03-10 Release Latest

New terms added:

ID	Label
OBID:0003250	biomedical laboratory organization
OBID:0003327	image data set
OBID:0003328	magnetic resonance image data set
OBID:0003329	magnetic resonance imaging participant
OBID:0003330	magnetic resonance imaging evaluant role
OBID:0003331	raw image data set
OBID:0003332	magnetic resonance pulse sequence protocol
OBID:0003355	image data set analysis
OBID:0003489	Scrub Typhus Detect IgM ELISA kit

GO:0006915

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/term/GO:0006915>

apoptotic process

Change Log

All changes	Term	Definition / Synonyms	Relationships	Cross-references	Other
Timestamp	Action	Category	Detail		
2020-11-13	Added	CONSTRAINT	never_in_taxon NCBITaxon:2 (Bacteria)		
2020-11-10	Added	CONSTRAINT	never_in_taxon NCBITaxon:4896 (Schizosaccharomyces pombe)		
2020-11-07	Deleted	SLIM	goslim_pombe		
2020-02-28	Deleted	XREF	MIPS_funcat:40.10.02		
2019-05-04	Added	XREF	MIPS_funcat:40.10.02		
2017-07-28	Added	SLIM	goslim_pombe		
2016-03-05	Added	SYNONYM	caspase-dependent programmed cell death		
2015-12-09	Added	CONSTRAINT	only_in_taxon NCBITaxon:33154 (Opisthokonta)		
2014-04-12	Added	DEFINITION	A programmed cell death process which begins when a cell receives an internal (e.g. DNA damage) or external signal (e.g. an extracellular death ligand), and proceeds through a series of biochemical events (signaling pathway phase) which trigger an execution phase. The execution phase is the last step of an apoptotic process, and is typically characterized by rounding-up of the cell, retraction of pseudopodes, reduction of cellular volume (pyknosis), chromatin condensation, nuclear fragmentation (karyorrhexis), plasma membrane blebbing		

The molecular function branch, before and after refactoring. The term marked with an 'x' in the left-hand panel has been obsoleted. Terms moved (assigned to a new parent) are indicated by arrows. New terms (right panel) are marked with 'NEW'. ¹The class label 'electron carrier activity' was changed to 'electron transfer activity'.

I love this! Now do this for the next 5 releases

Sorry, this was painstakingly hand-created by going over notes and commits...

How would a standardized change language help us?

Standard way to describe:

- Retrospective changes (“**diff**”)
 - What changes happened?
 - ... to this term?
 - ... to the ontology as a whole?
 - *To better understand and react to changes*
 - *Applications: Diff engines, summary tools, change visualization...*
- Prospective changes (“**apply**”)
 - What changes do I want to happen?
 - *To make contributing to an ontology more efficient*
 - *Applications: Patch engines, bots, ...*

How change requests are currently handled

Many ontologies are backlogged

monarch-initiative / mondo

210 Open ✓ 2,315 Closed

geneontology / go-ontology

723 Open ✓ 17,539 Closed

obophenotype / human-phenotype-ontology

746 Open ✓ 7,509 Closed

obi-ontology / obi

406 Open ✓ 870 Closed

The-Sequence-Ontology / SO-Ontologies

119 Open ✓ 482 Closed

(Note that these numbers are from December 2022)

Knowledge Graph Change Language (KGCL)

A taxonomy of change types

Vocabulary registered with w3id

A taxonomy of change types

<https://w3id.org/kgcl>

Classes

Class	Description
Activity	a provenance-generating activity
Agent	a provenance-generating agent
Change	Any change perform on an ontology or knowledge graph
ComplexChange	A change that is is a composition of other changes
MultiNodeObsolescence	A complex change consisting of multiple obsolescences
SimpleChange	A change that is about a single ontology element
EdgeChange	A change in which the element that is the focus of the change is an edge
EdgeCreation	An edge change in which a de-novo edge is created
MappingCreation	A specific kind of edge creation in which the

Intended to provide clarification

The screenshot displays a web interface for the concept 'node direct merge' (URI: <http://w3id.org/kgcl/NodeDirectMerge>). The interface is divided into several sections:

- Navigation:** Tabs for 'Annotation properties', 'Datatypes', and 'Individuals'. Below these are 'Classes', 'Object properties', and 'Data properties'.
- Class Hierarchy:** A tree view on the left showing various change types. The 'node direct merge' class is highlighted in purple. Other visible items include 'edge obsolescence', 'node obsolescence', 'node obsolescence with direct replacement', 'node obsolescence with no direct replacement', 'remove from subset', 'remove node from subset', 'subset membership change', 'add to subset', 'add node to subset', and 'remove from subset'.
- Annotations:** A central panel showing details for 'node direct merge'. It includes:
 - rdfs:label:** node direct merge
 - skos:definition:** An obsolescence change in which all metadata (including name/label) from the source node is deleted and added to the target node, and edges can automatically be rewired to point to the target node
 - skos:note:** In the OBO format serialization of the graph, the source node vanishes from the file as a distinct entry and is retained only as an alt_id

Hierarchical
classification of change
types

Documentation

KGCL allows for high-level abstractions

Low-level: RDF/OWL:


```
34681         <owl:annotatedTarget>Mood changes</owl:annotatedTarget>
34682         <oboInOwl:hasSynonymType rdf:resource="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/hp#layperson"/>
34683         </owl:Axiom>
34684 +         <owl:Axiom>
34685 +         <owl:annotatedSource rdf:resource="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/HP_0000712"/>
34686 +         <owl:annotatedProperty rdf:resource="http://www.geneontology.org/formats/oboInOwl#hasExactSynonym"/>
34687 +         <owl:annotatedTarget>Mood swings</owl:annotatedTarget>
34688 +         <oboInOwl:hasSynonymType rdf:resource="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/hp#layperson"/>
34689 +         </owl:Axiom>
~ ~ ~ ~ ~
```


High-level:

Add synonym “mood swings” to “emotional lability” (HP:0000712)

KGCL User-friendly syntax

A taxonomy of change types

<https://w3id.org/kgcl>

A Domain Specific Language (DSL)

- move T from $P1$ to $P2$
- add synonym “S” to T
- obsolete T

Knowledge Graph Change Language (KGCL)

A taxonomy of change types

<https://w3id.org/kgcl>

A Domain Specific Language (DSL)

- move *T* from *P1* to *P2*
- add synonym “S” to *T*

Machine Actionable Syntax

```
{
  "@type": "NewSynonym",
  "about": "HP:1234567",
  "new_value": "....."
}
```

Schema /
Shape

JSON Schema

validation

Class: NewSynonym

A node synonym change where a de-novo synonym is created

URI: kgcl:NewSynonym

Slots

Name	Cardinality and Range	Description	Inheritance
new_value	0..1 String	The value of a property held in the new instance of the ontology	direct
language	0..1 LanguageTag	The language tag of a literal	direct
qualifier	0..1 String	The qualifier of a change operation	direct
about_node	0..1 Node		NodeChange
about_node_representation	0..1 String	The representation of a node (URI, CURIE, label)	NodeChange
old_value	0..1 String	The value of a property held in the old instance of the ontology	SimpleChange

<http://w3id.org/kgcl/NewSynonym>

Knowledge Graph Change Language

Last uploaded: April 6, 2023

Summary

Classes

Properties

Notes

Mappings

Widgets

Jump to:

- activity
- agent
- broad
- change
 - complex change
 - simple change
 - edge change
 - edge creation
 - mapping creation
 - place under
 - edge deletion
 - remove under
 - edge logical interpretation change
 - edge obsolescence
 - edge rewiring
 - node move
 - node deepening
 - node shallowing
 - predicate change
 - logical axiom change
 - node change
 - add node to subset
 - node annotation change
 - node annotation replacement
 - node creation

Details

Visualization

Notes (0)

Class Mappings (157)

Preferred Name	activity
Synonyms	
Definitions	a provenance-generating activity
ID	http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Activity
definition	a provenance-generating activity
exactMatch	activity
label	activity
prefLabel	activity
subClassOf	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Thing

KGCL Formalism

- Change requests

- Aka “ontology patches”
- E.g. “**AddSynonym**”

$$O1 + \Delta \Rightarrow O2$$

- Describing existing changes

- Aka “ontology diffs”
- E.g. “*in the last month, there was an **AddSynonym** change*”

$$O1 - O2 \Rightarrow \Delta$$

Tools: OAK

The Ontology Access Kit (OAK) can:

- Diff:
 - Given two ontologies
 - Generate a KGCL file of all changes OR
 - Generate a SUMMARY file grouped by KGCL change types
- Apply
 - Given one ontology and a KGCL file
 - Apply changes to the ontology
 - Limitations:
 - Limited functionality and testing outside obo format

Tools: OntoBot

Add it to your GitHub repo

Watches for issues that invoke it (“Hey Ontobot!”)

Creates PRs

Looking for help: ROBOT/OWLAPI

What we would like:

- Robot diff to have a KGCL option
- A new robot “apply” command

Requires java/owlapi code

Tools: BioPortal changes UI

Allows logged in users to propose a select subset of change types

Opt-in ontologies only

- GO
- Uberon
- Mondo

Bioportal - OntoBot workflow

Details	Visualization	Notes (0)	Class Mappings (28)	🔗
Preferred Name	pregnancy disorder			
	pregnancy disorder complication, pregnancy pregnancy disease			
Synonyms	Complications, pregnancy disorder of pregnancy complication of pregnancy or childbirth disorder of pregnancy, childbirth, or puerperium pregnancy complication			

Bioportal - OntoBot workflow

I can take care of that for you!

Bioportal - OntoBot workflow

Current status:

- UI is released to production
- Features implemented:
 - Add new synonym (*NewSynonym*)
 - Remove existing synonym (*RemoveSynonym*)
 - Obsolete a Class (*NodeObsolesion*)
- Backend activated in production on the following ontologies
 - Mondo
 - Uberon
 - GO

Rote
issues

GitHub Actions

Hard
issues

BioPortal Change Request demo

Walk-through of the process for generating an ontology change request from the BioPortal application.

The screenshot displays the BioPortal interface for the Mondo Disease Ontology. The main header shows the ontology name and its last upload date (May 1, 2023). A navigation bar includes tabs for Summary, Classes, Properties, Notes, Mappings, and Widgets. The 'Classes' tab is active, and a 'Jump to:' search box is present. A list of classes is shown, with 'disease' selected. The details panel for 'disease' is open, showing its preferred name, synonyms, and a definition. A blue button labeled 'Add a proposal' is visible in the top right of the details panel.

Mondo Disease Ontology
Last uploaded: May 1, 2023

Summary **Classes** Properties Notes Mappings Widgets

Jump to:

- disease**
- disease characteristic
- disease susceptibility
- injury

Details Visualization Notes (0) Class Mappings (270)

Preferred Name disease

Synonyms disorders
condition
other disease
medical condition
disease or disorder
diseases
disorder
diseases and disorders
disease or disorder, non-neoplastic
disease

Definitions A disease is a disposition to undergo pathological processes that exists in an organism

[Add a proposal](#)

Demo: new synonym

Add synonym proposal for pregnancy disorder with abortive outcome ✕

Label

intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth

Type

exact

Comment

Demoing auto-generated ontology change requests from the BioPortal application

Close Submit

Demo: new synonym

Proposal: add synonym 'intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth' for pregnancy disorder with abortive outcome #136

New issue

Open kgcl-change-request opened this issue 3 minutes ago · 0 comments · May be fixed by #137

kgcl-change-request commented 3 minutes ago

Hey ontobot! apply:

- create exact synonym 'intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth' for MONDO:0041526

Comment: Demoing auto-generated ontology change requests from the BioPortal application

This request comes from BioPortal user: vendetti

Assignees

No one assigned

Labels

None yet

Projects

None yet

Milestone

No milestone

Development

Successfully merging a pull request may close this issue.

Proposal: add synonym 'intrauterine fetal de...

github-actions bot linked a pull request 1 minute ago that will close this issue

Proposal: add synonym 'intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth' for pregnancy disorder with abortive outcome #137

Open

Demo: new synonym

Proposal: add synonym 'intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth' for pregnancy disorder with abortive outcome #137

 Files changed **1**

github-actions bot commented 9 minutes ago ⋮

The following commands were executed:
* create exact synonym 'intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth' for MONDO:0041526

Fixes [#136](#)

 [create-pull-request] automated change 0ccfda4

 github-actions bot added the **Automated** label 9 minutes ago

This branch has no conflicts with the base branch

Reviewers

No reviews

Still in progress? [Learn about draft f](#)

Assignees

No one assigned

Labels

Automated

Projects

None yet

Milestone

.. .. .

Demo: new synonym

Proposal: add synonym 'intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth' for pregnancy disorder with abortive outcome #137

<> Code ▾

 Files changed 1

+1 -0

Changes from all commits ▾ File filter ▾ Conversations ▾ Jump to ▾

0 / 1 files viewed

Review in codespace

Review changes ▾

1

Viewed ...

	@@ -434698,6 +434698,7 @@ intersection_of: has_characteristic PATO:0002098 ! neoplastic, metastatic		
434698	[Term]	434698	[Term]
434699	id: MONDO:0041526	434699	id: MONDO:0041526
434700	name: pregnancy disorder with abortive outcome	434700	name: pregnancy disorder with abortive outcome
		434701	+ synonym: "intrauterine fetal demise (IUFD); intrauterine fetal death; stillbirth" EXACT []
434701	synonym: "pregnancy with abortive outcome" RELATED []	434702	synonym: "pregnancy with abortive outcome" RELATED []
434702	xref: ICD10CM:000-008 {source="MONDO:equivalentTo"}	434703	xref: ICD10CM:000-008 {source="MONDO:equivalentTo"}
434703	xref: SCTID:363681007 {source="MONDO:equivalentTo"}	434704	xref: SCTID:363681007 {source="MONDO:equivalentTo"}

Demo: obsolete class

Details

Visualization

Notes (0)

Class Mappings (3)

← Add a proposal

Proposal: obsolete 'metachromatic leukodystrophy, adult-onset, with normal arylsulfatase A'

Optionally enter a comment describing the reason for obsolesion

Submit

Cancel

Preferred Name

metachromatic leukodystrophy, adult-onset, with normal arylsulfatase A

Synonyms

metachromatic leukodystrophy, adult-onset, with normal arylsulfatase type A
metachromatic leukodystrophy, adult-onset, with normal arylsulfatase A

Demo: obsolete class

Proposal: obsolete 'metachromatic leukodystrophy, adult-onset, with normal arylsulfatase A' #134

Open

kgcl-change-request opened this issue 2 hours ago · 0 comments · May be fixed by #135

kgcl-change-request commented 2 hours ago

Hey ontobot! apply:

- obsolete MONDO:0007981

Comment: Recommended for obsolesion by the ClinGen expert panel. They note: This appears to be derived from an old entry in OMIM - no molecular details available.

This request comes from BioPortal user: vendetti

github-actions (bot) linked a pull request 2 hours ago that will close this issue

Proposal: obsolete 'metachromatic leukodystrophy, adult-onset, with normal arylsulfatase A' #135

Open

Assignees

No one assigned

Labels

None yet

Projects

None yet

Milestone

No milestone

Development

Successfully merging a pull request m

issue.

Proposal: obsolete 'metachromat
hrshdhgd/mondo

Demo: issue tracker for MONDO

210 Open	✓ 2,310 Closed	Author ▾	Label ▾	Projects ▾	Milestones ▾	Assignee ▾	Sort ▾
#5693 opened 4 minutes ago by nicolevasilevsky							
1							
#5690 opened 32 minutes ago by kgcl-change-request							
#5688 opened 1 hour ago by pnrobinson							
1							
#5687 opened 1 hour ago by pnrobinson							
1							
#5686 opened 1 hour ago by kgcl-change-request							

KGCL is not static!

- *A proposed* standard
- How can we make it better?
- Are the abstractions correct?
- Should it be extended for associations/KG edges?
- What changes do we need to make?
 - (we could describe them in KGCL but that may be too meta...)

Acknowledgements

- Current key contributors
 - Berkeley Lab: Chris Mungall, Harshad Hegde, Sierra Moxon
 - Stanford: Mark Musen, Jennifer Vendetti, John Graybeal
 - Beyond: Christian Kindermann (Knocean), HyeongSik Kim (Bosch), James Overton (Knocean), Nico Matentzoglu (semantically)

BioPortal
(U24 GM143402-01)

Bosch (SSSOM)

Monarch Initiative

Community discussion

Survey results

What is your role? (Check as many as apply)

41 responses

Survey results

How do you currently obtain information on ontology changes?

- BioPortal change summary
- Ontology release notes on GitHub
- Other ontology release notes
- Email summaries
- I do it myself using a tool (please specify tool, e.g. ROBOT diff)
- I don't
- Other: _____

How do you currently obtain information on ontology changes?

38 responses

Survey results

How do you communicate a desired change to an ontology?

- Make the change yourself and then create a Pull Request
- Create an issue in the issue tracker (using a template)
- Create an issue in the issue tracker (no template)
- Other: _____

How do you communicate a desired change to an ontology?

35 responses

What kind of summary statistics are useful for you? Rate the usefulness of each of these

slido

Which kinds of changes would you like to be applicable from ontology browsers? We saw obsolescence proposals and synonyms additions - what else would you like to see in Bioportal / OLS?

① Start presenting to display the poll results on this slide.

slido

What changes to you want to see in particular in an ontology release note? (e.g. new terms (ids, label), changed definitions, obsoletions, etc).)

① Start presenting to display the poll results on this slide.

slido

How useful do you personally (honestly!) think a formal language for describing changes in ontologies and knowledge graphs would be for your work?

① Start presenting to display the poll results on this slide.

slido

How important is the support of describing complex changes (arbitrary OWL axioms) for your use cases?

① Start presenting to display the poll results on this slide.

slido

How do you like the current design of KGCL at a first glance?

① Start presenting to display the poll results on this slide.

Use case 1: Understanding the changes of modelling immediately

- convincing yourself that the wrong entailments are fixed
- triaging consequential PRs for careful review

The screenshot displays the Protege ontology editor interface for the 'pizza' ontology. The main window is titled 'pizza (http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/pizza/pizza.owl)'. The interface is divided into several panels:

- Class Hierarchy:** Shows a tree view of classes. The 'SlicedTomatoTopping' class is highlighted, showing its parent 'TomatoTopping' and other subclasses like 'SundriedTomatoTopping'.
- Description:** Shows the description of the selected class, 'SlicedTomatoTopping', which is 'hasSpiciness some Mild'.
- Inference Inspector:** Displays a table of new inferences. The table has columns for 'P', 'OWL', 'Info', and 'G'. It lists various subClassOf relationships, such as 'NamedPizza SubClassOf Pizza' and 'SlicedTomatoTopping SubClassOf TomatoTopping'.
- Consequences of new assertions:** Shows a table of consequences. The table has columns for 'P', 'OWL', 'Type', 'Info', and 'G'. It lists violations, such as 'AmericanHot SubClassOf hasCountryOfOrigin value America' and 'AmericanHot SubClassOf hasTopping only'.

Use case 2: Systematic rewrites across releases

- Charlie: I would like to be able to rewrite an ontology systematically each time it is release
- Charlie: I would like to rewrite cross references systematically according to a context (e.g bioregistry)

Use case 3: Clement? Agroportal

Use case 4: Harry (KG OBO)

slido

What are some requirements you have for a language for describing ontology changes (perhaps beyond the ones that we discussed today)?

① Start presenting to display the poll results on this slide.

Future plans

- Implement community workshop recommendations
- Implement other change types
 - Remove synonym, move term, obsolescence, ...
- Start to design and develop the user interface for interacting with GitHub / WebProtege
- Proselytize UI and standard to community

Note: we plan to also allow for generating and visualizing diffs using KGCL, but this is for later in the cycle